

CHARACTERISTICS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED DENTISTRY STUDENTS IN THE UNIVERSITY OF THE EAST WITH DYSFUNCTIONAL HOMES

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Abstract: This study assessed the relationship of the characteristics and academic performances of dentistry students in the University of the East with dysfunctional homes. Parents play a major role in the formation of the child's behaviour. Child's behaviour can developed into the child's character which will give his or her identity. As everybody knows that "What we are today is how we were brought up by our parents." Parents guide, teach, discipline and motivate the children to be successful in their life. Parents were the first mentors that patiently taught everything to their children. At present, there were so many reasons why children do not live with their parents that affect the child physically, psychologically, emotionally, spiritually and intellectually as described in this study as "Characteristics of a person." The researcher used a research –made questionnaire to collect data from the third and fourth year dentistry students, enrolled in school year 2013-2014, using purposive sampling in the selection of the respondents. Frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, T-test, and Pearson Correlation were used to assess the relationship of academic performances of dentistry students with dysfunctional homes in basic medical and dental subjects. Based on the findings, the academic performances of the respondents in basic medical and dental subjects have no correlation with their characteristics. The result of the study would be of great help for dentistry students with dysfunctional homes and faculties that will guide the students.

Keywords: Academic performance, basic medical subjects, basic dental subjects, dysfunctional home.

I. INTRODUCTION

A Filipino's value to his or her family is evident in occasions. Unlike in the Western culture, holidays in the Philippines are spent with one's own families. Going home to their respective families in the provinces is a normal situation in the Philippines come holidays. In fact, the Philippines has a lot of holidays and most use these to be with their families. Whether it is a family picnic or swimming, hiking, karaoke, and a lot of other activities, the only important thing for the Filipino is to simply spend time with his or her family [1]. A dysfunctional home is one in which there is either abuse, neglect or both going on. The adults may not get along and might expose their children to terrible arguments or even physical fights. Conversely, the parents might be allies who care for and protect each other at the expense of their children. In a dysfunctional family, the parents are inadequate or abusive [2]. One of the primary functions of a family is to rear healthy children who get along well in the world outside the home. Parents in dysfunctional homes do not know how to do this. They tend to raise their children as they themselves were raised, transmitting destructive parenting practices from one generation to the next.

They typically have significant personal problems that interfere with their ability to focus on the welfare of their children. Children are expected to accommodate to chronic parental depression, substance abuse, marital conflict, or domestic violence. Adult family members may perceive themselves and their children in distorted ways, and make harsh, unfair judgments that damage children's self-esteem [3].

The family environment contributes to intellectual competence encompassing verbal expression, problem-solving skills, logical social competence, healthy relationships with members of the opposite sex, and sufficient education and training for economic autonomy. Poverty places children at a disadvantage because they are likely to experience abusive and dysfunctional home environments. The impact of a shift of the family from two parents to one can be traumatic. There have been hypotheses that children in families disrupted by separation are more likely to have emotional and behavioural problems. A dysfunctional home is one in which the relationship between parents and children is strained. This is due to the fact that one of the family members has a serious problem that affects other members who adopt atypical roles within the family to allow it to survive [4].

The changing role of women both at home and in the workplace, hold jobs outside the home either to supplement the husbands' earnings or to be the main and sometimes the only breadwinner in the family. This has led to the phenomenon of "househusbands". When the adjustment does not go well, women become overloaded and fatigued in trying to fulfill their duties as breadwinners working outside the homes and as housewives still taking care of the household. The significant increase in the number of OFWs or overseas Filipino workers resulted in the change in the structure and composition of our families.

Parental absence creates "displacement, disruptions and changes in care giving arrangement." There is always an emotional aspect that goes along with parents leaving their children, especially for long periods of time. Nevertheless, it is also a relief to have the extended family looking after the children left-behind. However, it cannot negate the fact that the children are longing for the love and care of their biological parents [5].

Dentistry is a demanding course in which undergraduates gradually develop their technical skills on a base of academic teaching about the physiology of the human body and more specifically, the still fast developing science behind dentistry. Recent decades have seen major advances in technology transforming the way dentists deal with issues both of tooth decay and patients' cosmetic concerns. The universities update students accordingly.

Typically, clinical work begins in the second year, with the first few terms in pre-clinical study. The emphasis will be on the basic medical sciences: first year subjects will include General Anatomy 1 (Regional Anatomy), General Microscopic Anatomy and Embryology, Biochemistry, Oral Anatomy, Dental History and Orientation, General Anatomy II (Head 6 and Neck), Oral Microscopic Anatomy and Embryology, General Physiology with Family Planning, Dental Materials, Nutrition and Computer Fundamentals and Dental Informatics. Second year includes General Pathology I and II, Pharmacology, Restorative Dentistry I and II, Prosthodontics I (Fixed Partial Denture), Microbiology, Oral Physiology and Occlusion, Prosthodontics II (Removable Partial Denture), Prosthodontics III (Complete Denture), Anaesthesiology, Orthodontics I (Growth and Development) and Roentgenology.

This academic work continues throughout the course. First year students start developing their dental skills. For instance, in Oral Anatomy, they learn to identify the tooth and the structures in the oral cavity, and carve the anatomy of each tooth. These are some of the dental skills which teachers develop among students of dentistry as early as in their second year they are already encouraged to handle live or actual patients in Restorative Dentistry II. These are the first dental subjects in which the students are required to apply the theories they have learned in Restorative Dentistry I, all of which are under clinical supervision. As they reach the higher level, they have more exposure to clinical dentistry as well as community involvement in dental practices. Students will have a chance to choose their line of specialization in fields such as paediatric dentistry, dental prosthetics, dental roentgenology and oral surgery. Years of intense work give the students the theoretical understanding and practical skills needed as foundation for the dental profession for it is believed that "Practice makes perfect."

If parents have concerns about their children's lack of developmental progress, they will want to discuss these concerns with their children's health care provider, and other professionals such as teachers, guidance counsellors, and school administrators [6]. The cause of poor academic performance of children is a combination of personal and institutional factors. The personal factors include the level of individual's intelligence, knowledge and ability, while institutional factors are family or parental influence. Maladaptive behaviour arise when parents lack responsibility of their parenthood and that

children that were raised from economically disadvantaged background are more likely to have poor academic performance because they lack some basic amenities such as food, clothing and shelter [7].

The way school buildings are structured, the way classrooms and students are organized reflect the cultural views of the society. The home, the family, the community likewise educate the people in the society [8]. Parents usually equate good education with private education. The common perception is that to give the best quality of education, parents must spend their life earnings. We have been losing our children to the Republic of Facebook. Children log thousands of hours using this modern form of social interface. Facebook makes human relationships “portable.” The final outcome is a child who knows nothing about the history of his or her nation, a child ignorant of the difference between a quark and an atom, and a child poorer by choosing Lady Gaga as an idol [9]. Nowadays, children found ways to forget their family problems for a short time by playing games in the computer like “candy crush” or “plants versus zombies” and other games, neglecting their school responsibilities because for them, school is an additional stress in their lives. At the elementary level, family involvement means supporting literacy, helping with homework, managing education and maintaining expectations, which in turn will result in the child’s motivation to achieve, quality work habits, and pro-social behaviour [10]. On a sad note, the children of migrant mothers reported being lonely, angry, unloved, unfeeling, afraid, different from the other children, and worried compared to all groups of children, including non -OFW children. But it was also evident that children of migrant mothers tend to score lower than the other children, and seems to suggest the importance of mother’s presence in the academic performance of the children [11]. Child trafficking is another result from dysfunctional homes almost all of these children are school dropouts from elementary or high school. They either work as domestic helpers or vendors to help augment family income When there is no food on the table, children are forced to drop out from school and try to look for jobs to help [12].

Bullying is global concern that has become prevalent in the workplace, schools and even in homes and it is prevalent because of the following reasons: Society tends to pick on someone who is different in appearance and someone who is weak and cannot defend himself. It is said that children that become bullies are victims themselves. They come from families where there is plenty of negative messages, harsh punishments and they see or experience bullying from their siblings and sometimes parents too. As a result, it may create false sense of self, poor social skills and may spill over into unhealthy treatment of others [13]. The study of [14] on parent-child relationship has been consistently associated with children’s development, adjustment, well-being and educational attainment. They are considered to be the core of family life because parents provide their children with a social capital for achieving long term goals and outcomes, global orientations toward interpersonal and social relationships, social support and understanding in challenging times such as the adolescent stage. They show aggressive tendencies and are unstable psychologically. They also do not trust others. Due to low self-esteem, they lack confidence, compare themselves negatively with others, and become isolated in the church. Further, due to the formation of a wrong concept of God, they do not have correct faith [15]. Study conducted by [16] as a result of the childhood abusive experiences and dysfunctional family dynamics, the pervasive characteristics of the childhoods of the men were confusion, unpredictability, rejection, secrecy, and fear.

The transition to college for the entering freshman encompasses a period of significant adaptational challenge and change, capable of resulting in heightened stress and potential crisis. Though many students adjust to this major life transition in a functional manner, others experience significant difficulty in attempting to navigate the multiplicity of development tasks occurring at this time. Poor adjustment among college students has been associated with a number of maladaptive adjustment responses. These responses include institutional attrition, depression, low self-esteem, suicide ideation, sexual and sleep disturbance, somatic distress, eating disorder, alcohol and drug abuse [17].

II. METHODOLOGY

The researcher employed the descriptive and supported by qualitative data obtained through interview. The descriptive method [18] uses quantitative method to describe what is gathering, analyzing, classifying, tabulating data about prevailing conditions making accurate interpretation using statistical treatment. It involves some types of comparison or contrast and attempts to discover relationship between non-manipulative variables. This method analyzes and interprets the academic performance of dentistry students with dysfunctional homes as respondents of the study.

In particular, the respondents of the study were the third and fourth year dentistry students of the University of the East enrolled during the school year 2013-2014. Each respondent was requested to answer the questionnaire and assess his or her academic performance.

In selecting the respondents, purposive sampling technique was used. Purposive sampling is the method of selecting the respondents of the study on the basis of the judgment of the sampler, who thinks that the result will be representative. Selection of the respondents will be based on their knowledge of the needed information. The following criteria were used as a guide in selecting the respondents. 1. Must be enrolled in the University of the East, College of Dentistry, School Year 2013-2014; and 2. Must be classified as dentistry students with dysfunctional homes as observed from their physical, psychological, emotional, spiritual and intellectual characters.

The researcher used the prepared questionnaire and checklist to gather data. The age, gender, civil status, year level, highest educational attainment of father and mother, number of siblings, order of birth, parents' status were included in the said instrument. The researcher recorded the academic performance in both basic dental and medical subjects of the dentistry students with dysfunctional homes as given by the respondents.

To validate the researcher-developed questionnaire, the researcher presented it to the dean, associate dean, department heads of the school of dentistry, section coordinators of the different clinical divisions and some clinical supervisors/faculty members for their comments and suggestions. The people who validated the instruments were not included in the final group of respondents. The recommendations or suggestions provided by the respondents were included in the questionnaire. The researcher personally distributed the said instruments for validation. Reliability of the questionnaire was also obtained and the computed Cronbach's Alpha is 0.921 which implies high reliability. With regard to data gathering, the researcher followed the procedure that provided information needed in the study.

There were several statistical tests used in this study to answer the specific objectives. Percentage distribution was used to describe the profile of the respondents. The characteristics of the respondents and the academic performance specifically their average were described using the mean. On the other hand, standard deviation was used to describe the dispersion of the responses and the academic performance of the students. Analysis of Variance was used to determine the significant difference in the characteristics and academic performance of the respondents grouped according to profile involving 3 or more groups like age, no. of siblings, order of births and others. Meanwhile, the t-test was used to compare their characteristics and academic performance when grouped according to their profile. To determine the degree of relationship between the characteristics and academic performance, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used. The statistical treatment of data was processed using the SPSS package of the CEU Center for Data Analysis.

III. RESULTS

The respondents of this study are students coming from dysfunctional Homes.

A. Age of the Respondents

It can be seen from Table 1, that most of the respondents belong to the age of 21 comprising 46 or 51.10 percent of them. This age is the expected age of the 3rd year students taking up Dentistry. This is followed by the age of 19-20 with 20 respondents corresponding to 22.2 percent.

Table I: Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent
19 -20	20	22.2
21-22	46	51.1
23-24	6	6.7
25-26	5	5.6
27 and above	13	14.4
Total	90	100.0

B. Parents' Status of the Respondents

Table 2 contains the parents' status of the respondents and it can be gleaned from the table most of them, that is, 56 or 62.2 percent have parents who are living together in spite of having dysfunctional homes. Furthermore 10 or 11.1 percent of the respondents have separated parents, 8 respondents or 8.9 percent their fathers are migrant workers, and 4 or 4.4 percent of the respondents have single parent (unmarried) while 2 of them have parents whose mother were migrant workers and the other have been divorced. These students are foreign students since there is no annulment here in the Philippines. There are 4 or equivalent to 4.4 percent of the respondents did not respond to their parents' status, they were in the state of denial.

Table 2. Parents' Status of the Respondents

Parent's Status	Frequency	Percent
Living Together	56	62.2
Separated	10	11.1
Father Migrant Worker	8	8.9
Single Parent (Unmarried)	4	4.4
Annulled	3	3.3
Mother Migrant Worker	2	2.2
Divorced	2	2.2
Both Migrant Workers	1	1.1
No response	4	4.4
Total	90	100.0

C. Students' Living Status

Table 3 contains the living status of the students and it can be noted from the table that 38 or 42.2 percent of the students are living with their parents and these are the students whose families are usually from Manila and from nearby provinces. Twenty seven of the respondents are living in the dormitories and these are likely to be from far provinces. There are 8 or 8.9 percent respondents live with their relatives and these students have no enough money to live in dormitories so their parents decided to ask their relatives to let their son or daughter to live with them. Since these students are not paying for the rentals and other utilities they were helping in the household chores so that their relatives will not feel that they were a burden to the family. Meanwhile 3 of the 90 respondents equivalent to 3.3 percent are living with friends. The closeness of friends are sometimes more than that of sisters and brothers that they are too familiar and at ease with each other that they want to be together all the time. Fourteen or 15.6 percent of the respondents were categorized as others because these students had no permanent living status.

Table 3. Students' Living Status

Students' Living Status	Frequency	Percent
Living with Parents	38	42.2
Dormitory	27	30.0
Living with Relatives	8	8.9
Living with Friends	3	3.3
Others	14	15.6
Total	90	100.0

D. Academic Performance of the Respondents in Basic Medical Subjects

Table 4 presents the academic performance of the respondents in their basic medical subjects. Dentistry students have nine (9) basic medical subjects and it can be seen from the table that they performed satisfactory in 3 of these subjects, fairly satisfactory in 4 subjects and barely satisfactory in the remaining 3 subjects. Furthermore, it can be observed that they obtained the highest mean rating in General Physiology with Family Planning ($\bar{x}=2.32$) followed by Nutrition ($\bar{x}=2.39$). On the other hand, their lowest performance is Pharmacology ($\bar{x}=3.01$) which is considered as one of the most difficult subjects in basic medical subjects. It needs a lot of understanding of the different actions and adverse effect of various drugs in the human body. It can be seen from the results that the students performed satisfactory in the basic medical subjects as shown by the overall mean which is 2.50.

Table 4. Academic Performance of the Respondents in Basic Medical Subjects

Basic Medical Subjects	Mean	S.D.	V.I.
Biochemistry	2.65	.580	Fairly Satisfactory
General Anatomy 1 (Regional Anatomy)	2.76	1.047	Fairly Satisfactory
General Anatomy 2 (Head and Neck)	2.55	.670	Fairly Satisfactory
General Microscopic Anatomy and Embryology	2.41	.659	Satisfactory
General Physiology with family Planning	2.32	.873	Satisfactory
Nutrition	2.39	.638	Satisfactory
General Pathology	2.51	.637	Fairly Satisfactory
Pharmacology	3.01	.755	Barely Satisfactory
Microbiology	2.79	.716	Barely Satisfactory
Overall Mean	2.50	.224	Satisfactory

E. Academic Performance of the Respondents in Basic Dental Subjects

Table 5 contains the results of the academic performance of the respondents in their 14 basic dental subjects. Tabular values show that the students performed “Satisfactory” in their basic dental subjects as shown by the overall mean of 2.50 with a standard deviation of .232. It can be observed from the table that the respondents performed “Satisfactory” in 6 of the 14 subjects while “Fairly Satisfactory” in the other basic dental subjects. They obtained their highest mean grade (\bar{x} =2.03) with a standard deviation of .508 in Dental Materials and followed by Orthodontics I (\bar{x} =2.22; S.D.=.471). Ranked third with the highest mean rating is in Dental History and Orientation (\bar{x} =2.28; S.D.=.471) and very close to this subject is Prosthodontics 1 (\bar{x} =2.29; S.D.=.535). Meanwhile, their lowest grade is in Anaesthesiology (\bar{x} =2.84; S.D.=.836) which is related to Pharmacology of basic medical subjects, followed by Oral Physiology and Occlusion (\bar{x} =2.74; S.D.=.665). Finally, ranked third with the lowest grade is in Oral Anatomy (\bar{x} =2.73; S.D.=.628) closely followed by Prosthodontics 2 (\bar{x} =2.72; S.D.=.591). As can be noted that when the students had the difficulty in Pharmacology it follows that Anaesthesiology in basic dental subjects will be difficult for them too.

Table 5. Academic Performance of the Respondents in Basic Dental Subjects

Basic Dental Subjects	Mean	S.D.	V.I.
Oral Anatomy	2.73	.628	Fairly Satisfactory
Dental History and Orientation	2.28	.471	Satisfactory
Oral Microscopic Anatomy	2.41	.765	Satisfactory
Dental Materials	2.03	.508	Satisfactory
Restorative Dentistry 1	2.59	.527	Fairly Satisfactory
Restorative Dentistry 2	2.53	.621	Fairly Satisfactory
Prosthodontics 1	2.29	.535	Satisfactory
Prosthodontics 2	2.72	.591	Fairly Satisfactory
Prosthodontics 3	2.47	.467	Satisfactory
Oral Physiology and Occlusion	2.74	.665	Fairly Satisfactory
Oral Pathology 1	2.61	.448	Fairly Satisfactory
Anaesthesiology	2.84	.836	Fairly Satisfactory
Orthodontics 1	2.22	.494	Satisfactory
Rocentgenology	2.54	.597	Fairly Satisfactory
Overall Mean	2.50	.232	Satisfactory

F. Perceived Characteristics of Dysfunctional Homes in Terms of Intellectual

Regarding the intellectual of the respondents as presented in Table 6, they often finish their projects (\bar{x} = 4.17; S.D. = .895) for if they cannot, consequence is they will get zero and great possibility to fail in class worst thing they do not want to happen. Meanwhile, they give their lowest assessment of focusing on subject matter (\bar{x} = 3.60; S.D.=.985). Young people like college students were thinking about many things. College students were considered “Children adult” wherein they were in the transition stage of early adulthood.

Table 6. Perceived Characteristics of Dysfunctional Homes in Terms of Intellectual

Characteristics in Terms of Intellectual	Mean	S.D.	V.I.
1. Can focus on subject matter	3.60	.985	Often
2. Rational	3.71	.968	Often
3. Finish projects	4.17	.895	Often
4. Understand things easily	3.81	.810	Often
Overall Mean	3.82	.678	Often

G. Comparison of the Academic Performance of the Respondents When Grouped According to Gender

It can be observed from Table 7, that there is a very significant difference in the academic performance of the male and female in basic medical subjects and in dental subjects as shown by the p-value which is less than 0.01 and 0.05 respectively. The obtained mean grade show that the female performed better than the male respondents in both subjects. Interviews revealed that female respondents can focused more because they want to make things light for their mothers or the aggrieved party and to show that even though they have dysfunctional homes they can still be successful in their academic performance. Female students are known to be more studious than the male and therefore they are likely to get higher grades than the male students

Table 7. Comparison of the Academic Performance of the Respondents When Grouped According to Gender

	Gender	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Significance
Basic Medical Subjects	Male	2.85503	.524192	4.081	P = 0.000 < 0.01 VS
	Female	2.45690	.391877		
Basic Dental Subjects	Male	2.61161	.336072	2.240	P = 0.028 < 0.05 S
	Female	2.43923	.356456		

H. Comparison of the Characteristics of Dysfunctional Homes when Grouped According to their Parents' Status

Table 8 contains the results of the comparison of the assessments of the students regarding their characteristics coming from dysfunctional homes. It can be viewed from the table that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the students as regards to their characteristics coming from dysfunctional homes. The results of the comparison of the characteristics of students from dysfunctional homes show that there is no significant difference in their assessment when they are grouped according to students' living status as shown by the p-value which are all greater than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 8. Comparison of the Characteristics of Dysfunctional Homes when Grouped According to their Parents' Status

	Parents' Status	Mean	S.D.	F-value	Significance
Physical	Annulled	1.905	.297	.540	P = 0.746 > 0.05 NS
	Separated	2.08571	.632456		
	Divorced	1.78571	.707107		
	Single Parent (Unmarried)	1.71429	.420560		
	Living Together	1.91255	.611112		
	Both Migrant Workers	1.71429	.349927		
	Total	1.89468	.567926		
Psychological	Annulled	2.48276	.604187	.976	P = 0.438 > 0.05 NS
	Separated	1.96539	.514039		
	Divorced	2.31034	1.024086		
	Single Parent (Unmarried)	1.83436	.286657		
	Living Together	2.07336	.505949		
	Both Migrant Workers	1.91189	.333046		
	Total	2.04854	.494378		
Emotional	Annulled	2.71212	.069433	.536	.748 NS
	Separated	2.50000	.613590		
	Divorced	2.55736	1.461660		
	Single Parent (Unmarried)	2.35227	.346917		
	Living Together	2.47250	.539513		
	Both Migrant Workers	2.24793	.326111		
	Total	2.45147	.528320		
Spiritual	Annulled	4.06667	.503322	.509	P = 0.769 > 0.05 NS
	Separated	3.96000	.983418		
	Divorced	4.00000	1.414214		
	Single Parent (Unmarried)	4.60000	.326599		
	Living Together	4.17364	.721935		
	Both Migrant Workers	4.29091	.683307		
	Total	4.17588	.738185		
Intellectual	Annulled	4.41667	.629153	.835	P = 0.529 > 0.05 NS
	Separated	3.92500	.928335		
	Divorced	4.12500	.176777		
	Single Parent (Unmarried)	3.56250	.850857		
	Living Together	3.82727	.671636		
	Both Migrant Workers	3.63636	.516764		
	Total	3.82941	.688135		

I. Comparison of the Academic Performance of the Respondents when Grouped According to Parents' Status

It can be gleaned from Table 9, that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of the students coming from dysfunctional homes when they are grouped according to their parents' status. This means that they just performed statistically the same even if the mean grade of the different groups differ numerically but their difference was not able to found a significant difference.

Table 9. Comparison of the Academic Performance of the Respondents when Grouped According to Parents' Status

Subjects	Parents' Status	Mean	S.D.	F-value	Significance
Basic Medical	Annulled	2.426	.334	2.270	P = 0.055 > 0.05 NS
	Separated	2.356	.330		
	Divorced	1.875	.570		
	Single Parent (Unmarried)	2.590	.173		
	Living Together	2.691	.522		
	Migrant Workers	2.452	.239		
	Total	2.589	.481		
Basic Dental	Annulled	2.458	.135	1.285	P = 0.279 > 0.05 NS
	Separated	2.414	.408		
	Divorced	2.000	.455		
	Single Parent (Unmarried)	2.371	.261		
	Living Together	2.537	.337		
	Migrant Workers	2.432	.347		
	Total	2.486	.346		

J. Relationship Between the Characteristics of Dysfunctional Homes and their Academic Performance

Table 10 indicates the relationship between the characteristics and the academic performance of the students who came from dysfunctional homes. It can be observed from the results that there is a negligible degree of relationship between the two variables but this relationship is found not to be significant as shown by the p-value which is greater than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 10. Relationship Between the Characteristics of Dysfunctional Homes and their Academic Performance

		Basic Medical Subjects	Basic Dental Subjects
Physical	r _s	.133	.175
	V.I.	Negligible Correlation	Negligible Correlation
	p-value	.215	.102
	Sig	NS	NS
Psychological	r _s	-.045	.112
	V.I.	Negligible Correlation	Negligible Correlation
	p-value	.673	.298
	Sig	NS	NS
Emotional	r _s	.058	.151
	V.I.	Negligible Correlation	Negligible Correlation
	p-value	.588	.158
	Sig	NS	NS
Spiritual	r _s	.126	.135
	V.I.	Negligible Correlation	Negligible Correlation
	p-value	.240	.209
	Sig	NS	NS
Intellectual	r _s	.169	.192
	V.I.	Negligible Correlation	Negligible Correlation
	p-value	.112	.072
	Sig	NS	NS

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: 1. The students performed fairly satisfactory to satisfactory in basic medical and dental subjects. 2. The respondents have positive physical, psychological, emotional, spiritual and intellectual characteristics. The academic performance in the basic medical and dental subjects of the respondents are statistically the same regardless of their profiles. 4. The academic performance of the respondents are the same in basic medical and dental subjects. 5. The characteristics of the respondents has nothing to do with their academic performance and vice-versa. In the light of the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are offered by the researcher: 1. The institution may come up with an activity to enhance and improve the physical and psychological well-being of the students from dysfunctional homes. 2. An academic program to help improve the performance of the male respondents like Learning Assistance Program (LAP) is recommended. 3. Interpreneurship program to encourage the students to develop their skills and generate income from such skills.

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